

RESEARCH ON THE AIR PERMEABILITY OF SPECIAL SLEEVE FILTER FABRICS
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF FLOUR MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES)

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Абстрактный.

В данной статье изучена воздухопроницаемость специальных рукавных фильтровальных тканей, используемых на предприятиях по производству муки, работающих в нашей Республике.

Abstract.

This article examines the air permeability of special filter sleeve fabrics used in flour production plants operating in our Republic..

Today, every sector is developing rapidly, and of course, industrial enterprises play a significant role in these developments. To take just one example, the volume of industrial production in our Republic in January 2025 amounted to 55.8 trillion soums, an increase of 4.3% compared to January 2024.[1] Currently, 44 flour mills, 48 seed shops, and 43 compound feed shops operate in the enterprises of the Uzdonmahsulot joint-stock company. [2] Industrial enterprises and other sectors emit more than 2 million tons of pollutants into the atmosphere annually. Flour-producing enterprises also emit harmful substances into the atmosphere along with dust. Scientists are conducting scientific research to solve such problems.

In order to reduce the impact of harmful substances, including dust from flour mills, there is an increasing demand for the development of special filter fabrics and their use in industrial enterprises. Currently, special filter fabrics are being produced in the textile industry from natural and synthetic fibers. One of the quality indicators of special filter fabrics is air permeability. Air permeability is an indicator that expresses the ability of the filter material to pass air. Air permeability mainly depends on the structure of the filter, porosity, density and thickness of the material. This parameter plays an important role in determining the efficiency of the filter, especially in air purification systems.

The air permeability of special filter fabrics is determined based on the standards GOST R EN 779-2014, GOST R EN 1822-1-2010, GOST R 51251-99, GOST 12088-77.

ASTM D737-18, published by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM), specifies a test method for measuring the air permeability of textile fabrics. This test method is applicable to many types of fabrics, including woven fabrics, nonwoven fabrics, air cushion fabrics, blankets, pile fabrics, knitted fabrics, and layered fabrics. These fabrics may be untreated, bulk, coated, resin-treated, or otherwise treated.[4]

The purpose of the research work is to determine the air permeability of non-woven sleeve filters currently used in flour enterprises and to produce woven sleeve filters that comply with state standards from local raw material yarns available in our Republic.

To produce this type of filter fabric, several non-woven sleeve filter samples were taken from the Surkhondaryodonmahsulotlari JSC enterprise and the air permeability of the samples was analyzed in the laboratory of the Termez State University of Engineering and Agrotechnology. The results of the analysis were performed using modern methods. The air permeability of the obtained samples is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

No	Samples	Values in units of measurement: cm ³ /cm ² /s
1.	I - sample	50.194
2.	II- sample	50.474
3.	III- sample	50.323
4.	IV- sample	50.194
5.	V- sample	49.444
Average value		50.125

Air permeability of various samples

Based on Table 1, a histogram of air permeability of the results obtained from various samples was developed, and the experimental samples were determined using the YG 461E device in the laboratory of the Termez State University of Engineering and Agrotechnology.

Air Permeability Tester YG 461E

The amount of air (cm³/cm²/s) passing through a tissue surface (1m²) per unit time (s) at a specified air pressure (5 mm Hg) is determined by the following formula:

$$B_{\Delta P} = \frac{V}{S\tau}$$

Here V is the volume of air, cm³; S is the surface area of the tissue, cm²; t is the time, sec..

Air flow passes through the pores of the textile material, so the air permeability indicators depend on the structural properties of the material, which determine its porosity, the number and size of pores. The air permeability of a fabric is also affected by the number, size and type of processing of pores on its surface, the number of layers and layers of fabric.[5]

In conclusion, the air permeability of samples of non-woven bag filters used in flour production enterprises was determined. The air permeability of non-woven bag filters was 50.125 cm³/cm²/s Pa. Based on this air permeability, it is recommended to design and manufacture bag filters based on fabric.

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